

HIDDEN TREASURES OF THE SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

A New Year's Gift for Students and Teachers of Quantum Mechanics

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It is by solving the Schrödinger equation that aspiring physicists first learn to make predictions about the quantum landscape at scales a billion times smaller than our human scale of everyday experience. The traditional guided tour introduces us to the Laguerre and Hermite polynomials and Airy functions, among others, and trains us to visualize consequences of the spherical harmonics. Acquiring this arcane knowledge, we gain entry into the company of initiates. It is even good fun—if you are a physics student—to develop a mastery of the special functions that builds on what is learned from the study of classical electrodynamics. By learning to make numerical solutions we expand the domain of physical situations for which we can derive predictions beyond those we can treat in closed form.

A complementary approach reveals interesting and useful relationships without the need for explicit solutions. In this holiday leaflet, I introduce a few of these *Schrödinger Shortcuts*, which I have occasionally presented in talks informally called “How to Cheat at Quantum Mechanics.” May they brighten the season and nourish your curiosity!

Historical Preliminaries

Johannes Kepler, born four-hundred-fifty years ago this week (*27 December 1571) and celebrated among physicists as discoverer of the three laws of planetary motion, was fascinated by Nature’s patterns. So taken was he with the snowflakes settling out of Prague’s winter skies that he began to ponder how, if every one was different from all the others, each was reliably hexagonal in form. Kepler documented his musings in a booklet of two dozen pages entitled *Strena seu De Nive Sexangula*, as the year 1610 turned to 1611. From his perch as Court Mathematician to Holy Roman Emperor Rudolf II, he offered his New Year’s gift, *On the Six-Cornered Snowflake* [1], to his friend and occasional patron, court counselor Johann Matthäus Wacker von Wackenfels. Wacker had brought Kepler the first news of Galileo’s discovery of Jupiter’s moons, the “Medicean stars.” Three centuries later, Kepler’s pamphlet remains a charming companion for a winter’s day.

The end-of-year holidays also have a special significance in the history of quantum mechanics, for it was during a retreat to the mountain village of Arosa in Switzerland at the end of 1925 that Erwin Schrödinger found inspiration for his invention of wave mechanics [2]. Schrödinger’s equation is a remarkably powerful tool for investigating atomic, molecular, and condensed-matter systems. It has never gone out of style, and it took on a new life in particle physics with the discovery of “atoms” of heavy quarks and antiquarks, beginning with the charm–anticharm states of the J/ψ family in 1974 [3].

When the Υ family of $b\bar{b}$ states was discovered in 1977, Jonathan Rosner and I joined the ranks of those who had been applying non-relativistic quantum mechanics very insightfully to the charmonium states. Comparing the two quarkonium systems, we came upon many results about quantum bound states that we had not known before. We mused that either they were new, or they had been forgotten for forty years. We summarized much of what we and others had learned in a small treatise on quarkonium quantum mechanics [4]. Now that those (re)discoveries are themselves four decades old, I highlight here a few of them for students, teachers, and aficionados of quantum mechanics.

The Schrödinger Equation

In three spatial dimensions, the Schrödinger Equation has the form

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu}\nabla^2\Psi(\mathbf{r}) + [V(\mathbf{r}) - E]\Psi(\mathbf{r}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\Psi(\mathbf{r})$ is the Schrödinger wave function, μ is the reduced mass of a two-body system, \mathbf{r} is the relative coordinate, $V(\mathbf{r})$ is the interaction

potential, E is the energy eigenvalue, and \hbar is Planck's constant divided by 2π . For a central potential $V(\mathbf{r}) = V(r)$, it is appropriate to express the Laplacian operator in spherical coordinates,

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2}. \quad (2)$$

Now we may separate the radial and angular dependences as

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}) = R(r) Y_{\ell m}(\theta, \phi), \quad (3)$$

where the angular dependence of a solution resides in a spherical harmonic, $Y_{\ell m}(\theta, \phi)$. With the substitution of Eqn. 3, the radial wave function for a state with angular momentum ℓ (in units of \hbar) satisfies

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \left(\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \right) R(r) - \left[E - V(r) - \frac{\ell(\ell+1)\hbar^2}{2\mu r^2} \right] R(r) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The radial equation simplifies if expressed in terms of a reduced radial wave function, $u(r) \equiv rR(r)$, that satisfies the boundary conditions

$$u(0) = 0 \quad u'(0) = R(0). \quad (5)$$

A prime denotes the derivative of a function with respect to its argument. The normalization condition on the Schrödinger wave function, $\int d^3\mathbf{r} |\Psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 = 1$, implies that $\int_0^\infty dr u(r)^2 = 1$.

The *reduced radial equation*,

$$-u''(r) = \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \left[E - V(r) - \frac{\ell(\ell+1)\hbar^2}{2\mu r^2} \right] u(r), \quad (6)$$

is the starting point for the observations that follow. It has the same form as the one-dimensional Schrödinger equation for an effective potential given by $[V(r) + \ell(\ell+1)\hbar^2/2\mu r^2]$, with the proviso that even-parity solutions in one (space) dimension do not satisfy the boundary condition $u(0) = 0$.

What can we learn from this equation without explicitly solving it? In this note, we will look at relationships that involve expectation values—averages—and we will see, by scaling the Schrödinger equation, how observables depend on the mass and coupling strength for power-law potentials. Many other insights, including semiclassical connections that link the level density with the shape of the potential or the probability density at the origin, and dualities between ionizing and confining power-law potentials, are introduced in [4].

A Little Magic Involving Expectation Values

Simple manipulations lead to numerous results of considerable general utility for the study of bound states in a central potential. Two informative connections illustrate the power of this approach.

Probability density at the origin

The absolute square of the s -wave ($\ell = 0$) wave function at the origin enters the calculation of hyperfine splitting. It is readily determined for a solution in closed form, but may be challenging to fix precisely for a numerical solution. We may evaluate $|\Psi(0)|^2$ in a different way by acting on both sides of the Schrödinger equation with $\int_0^\infty dr u'(r)$,

$$-\int_0^\infty dr u'(r)u''(r) = \int_0^\infty dr \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(r)]u(r)u'(r). \quad (7)$$

Next, use the identities $u'u'' = \frac{1}{2}(u'^2)'$ and $uu' = \frac{1}{2}(u^2)'$ to integrate by parts, obtaining

$$-\left. \frac{u'(r)^2}{2} \right|_0^\infty = \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(r)] \left. \frac{u(r)^2}{2} \right|_0^\infty - \frac{1}{2} \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \int_0^\infty dr [E - V(r)]' u(r)^2. \quad (8)$$

Evaluate and simplify to find

$$u'(0)^2 = R(0)^2 = 4\pi |\Psi(0)|^2 = -\frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(0)] \frac{u(0)^2}{2} + \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \left\langle \frac{dV}{dr} \right\rangle. \quad (9)$$

where the factor of 4π arises from $Y_{00} = 1/\sqrt{4\pi}$ (cf. Eqn. 3). Our first hidden treasure of the Schrödinger equation is the connection

$$\boxed{|\Psi(0)|^2 = \frac{\mu}{2\pi\hbar^2} \left\langle \frac{dV}{dr} \right\rangle}, \quad (10)$$

relating the wave function at the origin to the expectation value of the gradient of the potential.

A particularly neat application is to the case of a linear potential $V(r) = \lambda r$ that characterizes a particle tethered to an elastic string, the counterpart of Hooke's law in classical physics. The wave function at the origin is the same for all s -wave states; it is

$$|\Psi(0)|^2 = \frac{\mu}{2\pi\hbar^2} \left\langle \frac{dV}{dr} \right\rangle \longrightarrow \frac{\mu\lambda}{2\pi\hbar^2}. \quad (11)$$

We obtain this result—which exhibits the dependence on mass and coupling strength—without solving the Schrödinger equation or working out properties of the Airy functions.

Similar derivations carry through for all the partial waves, leading to expressions for the first nonvanishing derivative of the wave function at the origin.

Virial Theorem

To derive the virial theorem relating kinetic, potential, and total energies, we act on both sides of the Schrödinger equation with $\int_0^\infty dr r u'$:

$$-\int_0^\infty dr r u'(r) u''(r) = \int_0^\infty dr r \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(r)] u(r) u'(r) \quad (12)$$

Once again we integrate by parts. The left-hand side becomes

$$-\frac{1}{2} r u'(r)^2 \Big|_0^\infty + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty dr u'(r)^2 = \frac{1}{2} u(r) u'(r) \Big|_0^\infty = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty dr u(r) u''(r). \quad (13)$$

Using the Schrödinger equation to replace $u''(r)$, we find

$$-\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty dr \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(r)] u(r)^2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \langle E - V \rangle. \quad (14)$$

After integration by parts, the right-hand side of Eqn. 12 becomes

$$\frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} [E - V(r)] \frac{u(r)^2}{2} \Big|_0^\infty - \frac{1}{2} \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \int_0^\infty dr (r [E - V(r)])' u(r)^2. \quad (15)$$

Assembling the pieces, the kinetic energy $\langle T \rangle$ of the bound particle is

$$\boxed{\langle E - V \rangle \equiv \langle T \rangle = \left\langle \frac{r}{2} \frac{dV}{dr} \right\rangle}. \quad (16)$$

Power-law potentials offer interesting special cases of this second hidden treasure. For $V(r) = \lambda r^\nu$, with $-2 < \nu < \infty$, we find

$$\langle T \rangle = \left\langle \frac{r}{2} \nu \lambda r^{\nu-1} \right\rangle = \frac{\nu}{2} \langle V \rangle = \frac{\nu}{(2 + \nu)} E. \quad (17)$$

We recover at once the (perhaps) familiar relations for a Coulomb (or gravitational) potential, $\nu = -1$: $\langle T \rangle = -E = -\langle V \rangle/2$, and for a harmonic oscillator, $\nu = 2$: $\langle T \rangle = \langle V \rangle = E/2$. The logarithmic potential, $V(r) = C \ln(r/r_0)$, is a limiting case of the power laws as $\nu \rightarrow 0$. For it, all s -wave levels have a common kinetic energy, $\langle T \rangle = C/2$.

Scaling the Schrödinger Equation

For the special (but flexible) case of a power-law potential, $V(r) = \lambda r^\nu$, we may bring the Schrödinger equation to dimensionless form and infer directly how quantities with dimensions of energy or length depend on mass and coupling strength. Now the reduced radial wave equation is

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} u''(r) + [E - \lambda r^\nu - \ell(\ell + 1)\hbar^2/2\mu r^2] u(r) = 0, \quad (18)$$

in which the dimensionful parameters are $2\mu/\hbar^2$, E (with dimension $[E] = \mu$), and λ , which has dimensions $[\lambda] = [\hbar^{-\nu} \mu^{1+\nu}]$.

We may bring the Schrödinger equation of Eqn. 18 to dimensionless form by introducing a scaled measure of length,

$$\rho \equiv (\hbar^2/2\mu|\lambda|)^{1/\nu} r, \quad (19)$$

and expressing the energy eigenvalue as

$$E = (\hbar^2/2\mu|\lambda|)^{2/\nu} (\hbar^2/2\mu)\varepsilon, \quad (20)$$

where ε is dimensionless. The resulting equation becomes free of dimensionful quantities if we set

$$p = -1/(2 + \nu) \quad (21)$$

and substitute $w(\rho)$ for $u(r)$. The scaled Schrödinger equation,

$$w''(\rho) + [\varepsilon - \text{sgn}(\lambda)\rho^\nu - \ell(\ell + 1)/\rho^2]w(\rho) = 0, \quad (22)$$

does not depend on either μ or λ .

We see (*cf.* Eqn. 20) that level spacings scale with mass and coupling strength as

$$\Delta E \sim (2\mu/\hbar^2)^{-\nu/(2+\nu)} |\lambda|^{2/(2+\nu)}, \quad (23)$$

with these notable consequences:

Potential	Power ν	$\Delta E \sim$
Coulomb	-1	$\mu \lambda ^2$
$r^{-1/2}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$\mu^{1/3} \lambda ^{4/3}$
Logarithmic	$\rightarrow 0$	$\mu^0 C$
Linear	1	$\mu^{-1/3} \lambda ^{2/3}$
Harmonic Oscillator	2	$\mu^{-1/2} \lambda ^{1/2}$
Infinite Square Well	$\rightarrow \infty$	μ^{-1}

Now looking back to Eqn. 19, we find that lengths scale as

$$L \sim (2\mu|\lambda|/\hbar^2)^{-1/(2+\nu)}, \quad (24)$$

which implies the following scaling laws for power-law potentials.

Potential	Power ν	$L \sim$	$ \Psi(0) ^2 \sim$
Coulomb	-1	$(\mu \lambda)^{-1}$	$(\mu \lambda)^3$
$r^{-1/2}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$(\mu \lambda)^{-2/3}$	$(\mu \lambda)^2$
Logarithmic	$\rightarrow 0$	$(\mu C)^{-1/2}$	$(\mu \lambda)^{3/2}$
Linear	1	$(\mu \lambda)^{-1/3}$	$(\mu \lambda)^1$
Harmonic Oscillator	2	$(\mu \lambda)^{-1/4}$	$(\mu \lambda)^{3/4}$
Infinite Square Well	$\rightarrow \infty$	(μ^0)	(μ^0)

The hidden treasures of the Schrödinger equation are truly wondrous to behold. Happy exploring!

Bibliography

- [1] A recent edition, with commentary, is Johannes Kepler, *The Six-Cornered Snowflake*, (Paul Dry Books, Philadelphia, 2010), ISBN 978-1-58988-053-5.
- [2] The story of Schrödinger’s winter inspiration is told in many places, including Walter J. Moore, *Schrödinger: Life and Thought* (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1989) “Discovery of wave mechanics, pp. 191–229. See E. Schrödinger, “Quantisierung als Eigenwertproblem (Quantization as an eigenvalue problem),” *Annalen der Physik* 79, 361, 489 (1926); 80, 437 (1926); 81, 109 (1926). For English versions, see J. F. Shearer and W. M. Deans, translators, *E. Schrödinger, Collected Papers on Wave Mechanics*, (Blackie and Son, London, 1928). A short documentary film (in German), Thomas Gull & Stephan Läubli, “Erwin Schrödinger—Eros und Atome” vimeo.com/279665873, follows Zürich physicist Laura Baudis on a winter pilgrimage to Arosa.
- [3] I recounted some of the history in C. Quigg, “Celebrating Quarkonium: The First Forty Years,” doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5812403 Seminar presented at CERN during the 2014 meeting of the Quarkonium Working Group, marking the fortieth anniversary of the discovery of the J/ψ (charmonium) family of heavy mesons. The slides containing many links to the original literature. I chose a different historical approach at the 2024 SLAC Summer Institute, describing

the world into which J/ψ was born: “The Night before Charmonium,” doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14844786.

- [4] C. Quigg and J. L. Rosner, “Quantum Mechanics with Applications to Quarkonium,” Phys. Rept. 56, 167-235 (1979), FERMILAB-PUB-79-022-T.